

In conclusion, the relationships can be paralleled as follows:

Urukagina (the last ruler of Lagaš I)	Lugalzagesi of Uruk III
Ur-Ningirsu I (the first ruler of Lagaš II)	Sargon of Akkad
Pirigme	Rimuš and Man-ištuš of Akkad
Kaku	
Lugal-ušumgal ⁶⁾	Naram-Sîn of Akkad
Ur-Ba'u	Šar-kali-šarri of Akkad
Ur-GAR	
Nammaḥni	Jarlagan of Gutium
Ur-abba	Ur-Namma of Ur III

Notes

1. See the concluding scheme in MAHIEU 2019: 22.
2. WILCKE 2011: 34 n. 22, 35-37.
3. SALLABERGER & SCHRAKAMP 2015: 28-31, 120 and n. 417; cf. MICHALOWSKI 2013: 180-181.
4. SALLABERGER & SCHRAKAMP (2015: 130 [Table 36]), however, differentiate Nammaḥni of Umma from Nammaḥni/Namḥani of Lagaš. MONACO (1990: 98-99), on the other hand, differentiates Nammaḥni of Lagaš and Umma from Namḥani of Lagaš.
5. WESTENHOLZ 1984: 339: “In view of these two references, it seems certain that Lagash at this time was under the sway of the ruler of Ur.” Westenholz, however, differentiates Kaku of Ur from Kaku of Lagaš II because of the conventional two centuries between Rimuš (the contemporary of Kaku of Ur) and Ur-Namma (the contemporary of Nammaḥni of Lagaš II, the grandson of Kaku).
6. Lugal-ušumgal, who is ÉNSI of Lagaš in the days of both Naram-Sîn (RIME 2.1.4.2004) and Šar-kali-šarri (RIME 2.1.5.2004), should be inserted in the sequence.

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6) KI.ŠEŠ.KAK(A) — D’après P. Steinkeller (NABU 2020/106), il n’y aurait “no doubt that the meaning of the logogram in question is ‘(the one) erected (du₃-a) in a brackish (sis) ground (ki)’”. Un argument ténu en faveur de son hypothèse pourrait être la graphie non-standard ka-ses-a dans Enlil A 45 N₁₆, quoiqu’on voie mal pourquoi ka aurait évolué en ki¹⁾.

Une alternative à mon sens préférable est toutefois de lire KI.ŠEŠ.KAK(.A) ki urin du₃(-a) “lieu où sont plantés les étendards” (v. déjà P. Attinger, *CM* 50 [2020] 84). Dans deux passages en effet, kissa-k est associé aux étendards:

Enlil A 45 sq. (variantes non notées): kissa urin mul-la-ba / di-ir-ga me ul-e šu im-ta-du₇-du₇ “*Sur ses (de l’Ekur) murs de soutènement, où scintillent les étendards, les arrangements rituels et les ordonnances culturelles sont exécutés à la perfection.*”

Löhnert, AOAT 365, 181:18 = 409:15 (variantes non notées): kissa-ka urin mul-la-ta “*Depuis les étendards scintillant sur les murs de soutènement (...)*”²⁾.

Note

1. Si KA.ŠEŠ.A est une graphie fautive pour KA.ŠEŠ<.KAK>.A = /kassa/, /ka/ s’expliquerait facilement par l’harmonie vocalique (/kissa/ > /kassa/). Une graphie phonétique ka-ses-a serait enfin aussi envisageable, quoique ka- fasse dans ce cas également difficulté.

2. Vu kissa-ka (pas kissa), la traduction contextuellement préférable “*Depuis les murs de soutènement, où scintillent les étendards (...)*” semble exclue.

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7) An Ur III Account of Fish from Umma — The tablet here published belongs to a private collection in the United States, whose whereabouts are currently unknown. I wish to thank Professor Piotr Steinkeller for having kindly allowed me to study the material in his possession, which he originally received from Edward Praczukowski, former Professor of Art at the University of Washington. The tablet comes from the Ur III provincial archive of Umma and records a fish delivery to the institutional economy.

obverse

1. ʾ236¹ ku₆ ḡi²hal
2. ki ur-^dkal-kal-ta
3. 37 ku₆ hal 0.0.5-ta
4. 1290 ku₆ kun-zi
5. 1620 ku₆ saḡ-/kur₂
6. ki amar-i₃-sin₂¹(TU)-ta
7. 67 ku₆ hal 0.0.5 4-ta

reverse

8. 1080 ku₆ kun-zi
9. 1920 ku₆ saḡ-/kur₂
10. ʾki¹ ba-da-ga-ta
11. šu-niḡin₂ 2370 ku₆ kun-zi
12. šu-niḡin₂ 3540 ku₆ saḡ-/kur₂
13. šu-niḡin₂ 340 ku₆ hal
14. e₂-kišib-ba-ka ku₄ (KWU147)-ra
15. ḡiri₃ ur-niḡar_x^{ḡar}

“(1-2) 236 *hal*-baskets¹⁾ of fish from Ur-Kalkal; (3-6) 37 *hal*-baskets of fish of 50-litre capacity each, 1290 pond fish, 1620 “headed” fish, from Amar-Isin; (7-10) 67 *hal*-baskets of fish of 54-litre capacity each, 1080 pond fish, 1920 “headed” fish, from Badaga. (11-14) Totals: 2370 pond fish, 3540 “headed” fish, 340 *hal*-baskets of fish, entered in the warehouse; (15) conveyor Ur-niḡar”.

